

Metachromatic Interactions of Pinacyanol with some Acid Polysaccharides†

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Chaotic aggregation of the dye pinacyanol chloride (PCYN) with dextran sulphate (DS) is reflected in its exhibition of multiple banded metachromasia. Shapes of the metachromatic curves for the PCYN-DS system remain insensitive towards changes of polymer to dye mole ratio (P/D) at least up to 30.0. PCYN also exhibits flat multiple banded metachromasia with Bael (*Aegle marmelos*) exudate gum polysaccharide (BP). Bael fruit gum polysaccharide, AMA, having very low charge density causes metachromatic spectral shift of PCYN at relatively higher P/D (30.0). Half-plateau values signifying disruption of metachromasia to the extent of 50 per cent corresponds to ~63, ~26 and ~21% ethanol for PCYN-DS, PCYN BP and PCYN-AMA systems respectively.

WE reported earlier¹ the metachromatic interactions of thiazine dyes with some acid polysaccharides differing widely in charge densities. Nature²⁻⁶ of the polyanion sharply influences its interaction with the cyanine dyes. Here we report our observations on interactions of cyanine dye pinacyanol chloride (PCYN) with different acid polysaccharides and the effect of disruptive factors like ethanol on the different systems.

Experimental

The isolation of Bael exudate gum polysaccharide¹ (BP) and Bael fruit gum polysaccharide² (AMA) was described earlier².

Dextran sulphate (DS), chondroitin sulphate (CS), pinacyanol chloride (PCYN) (Serva, Feinbiochemica, Heidelberg) were used as such. Heparin (Hep) was received as gift from Central Drug Laboratory, Calcutta.

Stock solutions of the dye was made in 5 ml methanol and then making up the volume to 100 ml with double-distilled water and stored in dark.

Equivalent weights of the polysaccharides were determined through conductometric titrations^{3,7,8} and conductances were measured with a Systronics conductometer. Absorbances were measured with a Bausch & Lomb visible spectrophotometer or a Toshniwal digital spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Cyanine dyes are characterised by the strongly

charged chromophoric group, $N=C-\overset{\oplus}{|}C-\overset{|}{|}C-\overset{|}{|}N$, where $n=1, 2$ etc.

In contrast to rigid planar structural pattern of thiazine, oxazine, acridine or pyronine dyes a

cyanine dye is more flexible in being able to be heteroplanar or to have *cis-trans* isomers. Interactions of cyanine dyes are influenced by polyanionic charge density, flexibility and conformation of polymer chain and stoichiometry of dye-polyanion system³⁻⁶.

Fig. 1A shows the absorption spectrum of $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ pinacyanol chloride solution. Intense aggregating tendency of PCYN is evident from the

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of (A) $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ pinacyanol chloride (PCYN) in water, in presence of (B) DS at P/D=3.0, (C) BP at P/D=6.0, (D) AMA at P/D=1.0 and (E) 30.0.

† A part of the work was presented at the 26th Annual Convention of Chemists held at Indore, 1989.

appearance of its prominent dimer band (β -band) around 547 nm even at this dilution in addition to its monomer band (α -band) around 600 nm. West and Pearce³ reported sharp single banded metachromasia in PCYN caused by dye aggregate in the absence of any added polyanion. The ordered aggregation of dye cations leads to sharp single banded metachromatic shift. The chaotic aggregation of dye cations results in broad multiple banded metachromasia in presence of certain polyanion⁵ and also in presence of DS, BP and AMA. DS (Eq. wt. 167, charge density 2.0 per monosaccharide unit) induces metachromasia in PCYN with a sharp peak at 485 nm followed by a broad band with peak around 525 nm (Fig. 1B). Positions of the metachromatic bands and shapes of the metachromatic curves are insensitive towards changes of P/D at least up to 30.0 (curves not shown). BP (Eq. wt. 854, charge density 0.19) causes flat multiple banded metachromasia in PCYN with peak around 490 nm followed by appreciable absorbance around λ_{\max} of the dye (Fig. 1C). The shapes of the curves of BP-PCYN system are also not influenced by changes in P/D (curves not shown). AMA (Eq. wt. 2055, charge density 0.074) does not cause spectral shift of PCYN at P/D 1.0 (Fig. 1D) and 2.0 (curve not shown). With the increase of P/D to 3.0 and 9.0 (curves not shown) broad shoulders appear towards shorter wavelength with appreciable absorbances around λ_{\max} of the dye. Flat multiple banded metachromatic curve (Fig. 1E) corresponds to PCYN-AMA system at P/D 30.0. Nature of induction of metachromasia reflects weak chromotropic abilities of AMA and BP. In fact induction of metachromasia by polyanions of such low charge densities as AMA and BP has been rarely reported. AMA and BP have been reported¹ to cause metachromasia of highly metachromatic thiazine dye, 1,9-dimethyl methylene blue, but they fail to do so with methylene blue and toluidine blue, both belonging to the same thiazine group.

Fig. 2 shows the influence of ethanol over the metachromatic compounds of PCYN with DS, BP and AMA. The extent of the destruction of metachromasia with the use of increasing concentration of ethanol grades the stability of metachromatic compounds. Decrease in stability of metachromatic compounds is accompanied by increasing absorbance of the dye-polyanion solution at the monomer band (α -band) and the decreasing absorbance at metachromatic band (μ -band). Half-plateau value^{1,10} derived from half-way between the lower level of absorbance approached at low ethanol concentration in presence of the strongest chromotrope and the upper plateau value approached or reached for each family, signifies the disruption of metachromasia to the extent of 50% per cent. This corresponds to 63, 26 and 21% ethanol for PCYN-DS (P/D=

Fig. 2. Absorbance at the α -band of (A) $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ (PCYN) vs per cent ethanol in water, in presence of (B) AMA at P/D=30.0, (C) BP at P/D=6.0 and (D) DS at P/D=3.0; curves (E), (F) and (G) show the corresponding absorbances at the μ -band vs per cent ethanol.

3.0), PCYN-BP (P/D=6.0) and PCYN-AMA (P/D=30.0) systems respectively.

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